

TABLE 2—IR BANDS OF COMPLEXES

Compd.*	$\nu_{C=N}$ cm ⁻¹	ν_{N-O} cm ⁻¹
Ni(DMGH) ₂	1 576	1 241
Pd(DMGH) ₂	1 552	1 259
X (Li8HQ) ₂	1 586	1 230
X.(Na8HQ) ₂	1 590	1 226
X.(K8HQ) ₂	1 586	1 229
X (Li1N2N) ₂	1 586	1 214
X.(Na1N2N) ₂	1 590	1 220
X.(K1N2N) ₂	1 580	1 214
Y.(Li1N2N) ₂	1 572	1 206
Y.(K1N2N) ₂	1 560	1 212

*X—Ni(DMGH)₂, Y—Pd(DMGH)₂.

exposure to moisture. Electronic spectra were recorded on a Varian-Carry 14 spectrophotometer in nujol.

Results and Discussion

The C=N frequency of Ni(DMGH)₂ at 1 576 cm⁻¹ shifts to 1 580–1 590 cm⁻¹ in the alkali metal adducts; and the corresponding C=N of Pd(DMGH)₂ at 1 552 cm⁻¹ shows the upward trend in its adducts, observed at 1 560–1 572 cm⁻¹. Similar upward trend of C=N was observed for Pd/Ni(DMG)₂(BF₃)₂¹. The C=N stretching frequencies of alkali metal oxinates were observed at 1 550–1 540 cm⁻¹ (being part of the aromatic ring) and remain unchanged in the trinuclear adducts. The ν_{N-O} of Ni(DMGH)₂ at 1 241 cm⁻¹ shows a downward trend to 1 214–1 230 cm⁻¹ in the alkali metal adducts. For Pd(DMGH)₂, the ligand ν_{N-O} at 1 259 cm⁻¹ shifts to 1 206–1 212 cm⁻¹ in the alkali metal adducts. The observations of other workers²⁻⁵ on pyridine-N-oxide complexes, are similar. The ν_{N-O} of the 1N2N becomes a part of the ring in its alkali metal salt, and attains some double bond character as ν_{N-O} is observed at ~1 340 cm⁻¹. The C—O bond of alkali oxinates, being a part of the ring, attains a partial double bond character, and ν_{C-O} is observed at 1 520–1 500 cm⁻¹.

The electronic absorption band of medium intensity at 475 nm for Ni(DMGH)₂ and [Ni(DMG)₂(BF₃)₂], and at 510 nm for trinuclear alkali metal adducts derived from Ni(DMGH)₂ suggest that even in these trinuclear adducts, the central Ni^{II} retains its square-planar structure. All compounds of Ni^{II} are diamagnetic.

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Studies on Manganese(II), Cobalt(II), Nickel(II) and Zinc(II) Complexes of Substituted Aryl Furyl β -Diketones

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β -Diketones are well known for their biological activity¹. They are known to act as inhibitors against galvanic corrosion². Attempts have been made to evolve analytical methods for iron and steel by direct dissolution of metal in β -diketones³. The application of their metal complexes in various diverse fields such as column, thin layer and gas chromatography, solvent extraction, laser technique, nmr shift reagent and in polymer industry is however of comparatively recent origin⁴. Therefore, β -diketones have been extensively investigated for their complex forming ability⁵. The present study was undertaken with a view to investigate systematically the complex formation process between some transition metal ions and aryl furyl β -diketones.

- 1; R = CH₃, R₁ = R₂ = H
- 2; R₁ = CH₃, R = R₂ = H
- 3; R₂ = CH₃, R = R₁ = H

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. The β -diketones, 1-(2-furyl)-3-(3',4'-dimethyl-2'-hydroxyphenyl)propane-1,3-dione (F-3',4'-DMPPD) (1), 1-(2-furyl)-3-(3',5'-dimethyl-2'-hydroxyphenyl)propane-1,3-dione (F-3',5'-DMPPD) (2) and 1-(2-furyl)-3-(3',6'-dimethyl-2'-hydroxyphenyl)propane-1,3-dione (F-3',6'-DMPPD) (3) were prepared and purified by the methods described earlier⁶. The metal ions were used in the form of their nitrates and were estimated by EDTA titrations⁷. Dioxane was purified by the standard method⁸.

The Calvin-Bjerrum titration technique involved the titrations of (i) $4 \times 10^{-3} M$ HClO₄, (ii) $4 \times 10^{-3} M$ HClO₄ + $2 \times 10^{-3} M$ ligand, and (iii) $4 \times 10^{-3} M$ HClO₄ + $2 \times 10^{-3} M$ ligand + $4 \times 10^{-4} M$ metal ion solutions against standard ($1.833 \times 10^{-2} N$) carbonate-free NaOH solution.

An approximate quantity of 1 M NaClO₄ solution was added to each of the above mixtures to maintain constant ionic strength of 0.1 M. The total volume of each of the mixtures was made up to 50 ml so that the solutions were 50% (v/v) with respect to dioxane. A Elico LI-120 pH meter (accuracy of ± 0.01 pH unit) with glass and calomel electrodes, was used to record the pH values. All the measurements were carried out at $30 \pm 0.1^\circ$. These practical values were converted into thermodynamic values by applying Van Uitert and Fernelius correction⁹. The deprotonation constants of the ligands along with the stability constants of the metal–ligand complexes evaluated by the procedure of Irving and Rossotti¹⁰ are presented in Table 1.

TABLE 1—PROTON-LIGAND AND METAL-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS OF TRANSITION METAL- β -DIKETONE COMPLEXES IN 50% (v/v) AQUEOUS DIOXANE

Metal ion	F-3',4'-DMPPD		F-3',5'-DMPPD		F-3',6'-DMPPD	
	log K ₁	log K ₂	log K ₁	log K ₂	log K ₁	log K ₂
H ⁺	8.88	—	9.34	—	8.77	—
Ni ²⁺	6.51	5.13	6.22	4.68	5.52	3.65
Co ²⁺	6.07	5.24	5.98	4.65	5.23	3.54
Zn ²⁺	5.76	4.80	5.68	4.60	5.02	3.43
Mn ²⁺	4.90	4.43	4.85	4.50	4.70	3.35

Temp. = 30°, μ = 0.1 M NaClO₄
Standard deviation : ± 0.02 .

Results and Discussion

The pK values of acetylacetone, benzoylacetone, dibenzoylmethane and 2-furoylbenzoylmethane are 12.70, 12.85, 13.75 and 12.95, respectively, in dioxane–water (3 : 1) medium⁹. In these compounds, however, there is no phenolic OH groups and hence pK values refer to the deprotonation of the compounds in their enol form due to keto-enol tautomerism. The deprotonation for present β -diketones refers to the phenolic OH group and comparable to pK value (10.50) of phenol¹¹ in 1 : 1 (v/v) dioxane–water medium. Thus, there is lowering of pK values (*i.e.* increase in acid strength) for the present ligands. The second deprotonation arising out of keto-enol tautomerism of these ligands could not be followed in the present study.

The difference between log K₁ and log K₂ of metal–ligand complexes were less than 1.78 log units, suggesting overlapping of the successive formation of both the complexes. The formation for the metal complexes with F-3',5'-DMPPD, and F-3',6'-DMPPD were however incomplete due to precipitation. The log K₂ values in these cases were therefore calculated by the mid-point method¹⁰ using equation, $\log K_1 K_2 = 2 pL$ (at $\bar{n} = 1.0$). With respect to ligands, the stability sequence was F-3',6'-DMPPD < F-3',4'-DMPPD < F-3',5'-DMPPD, and this should be in accordance with their basicities. The stability of the

different complexes investigated follow the order, Ni²⁺ > Co²⁺ > Zn²⁺ > Mn²⁺ which is in accordance with Mellor and Malley¹². There was a linear relationship between log K and pK values suggesting identical binding sites in all the ligands.

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Dithiocarbamate Anions as Salts of Oxinatobis-(η^5 -indenyl)titanium(IV)/zirconium(IV) Chelates

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DURING the course of our recent investigations¹⁻³ we have elucidated that the coordination of two nitrogen and two oxygen atoms to (η^5 -R) (η^5 -R')M(IV) moiety would lead to the weakening of the metal ring bonds (R=C₄H₄N, R'=C₅H₅, C₅H₇; R=C₅H₅, R'=C₅H₇; M=Ti,